

Performance and degradation analysis of sputter deposited thin-film platinum cathodes in PEM water electrolyzers analyzed by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

Supplementary Information

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Figure S1: SEM images of sputter-etched membranes, sputtered over with increasing Pt loadings: a) *MEA 0 μg*, b) *MEA 3.7 μg*, c) *MEA 7.5 μg*, d) *MEA 15 μg*, e) *MEA 30 μg*, f) *MEA 60 μg*, g) *MEA 120 μg*, h) *MEA 240 μg*, and i) *MEA 480 μg*. All images share the identical view field of 5.0 μm, the scalebar is placed in part h).

Figure S2: Graphical representation of the electrochemical measuring procedure.

Figure S3: a) Equivalent Electrical Circuit (EEC) used for the fitting the spectra. b) Example of a measured PEIS spectrum showing three distinguishable resistances: ohmic resistance R_{Ω} , cathodic charge transfer resistance R_c , and anodic charge transfer resistance R_a .

Figure S4: IV curves of cycle 6 of samples $MEA\ 240\ \mu g$ and $MEA\ 240\ \mu g\ v2$. The graph demonstrates the high reproducibility of the sputter-etching treatment and magnetron sputtering process, confirming the consistency of the MEA with the best performance among all the samples tested.

Figure S5: IV curves of MEAs with a Pt loading of $120 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ pair after the break-in period in cycle 4. The *MEA 120 μg* with a sputter-etched modified cathode outperformed its non-etched counterpart, achieving almost twice the performance.

Figure S6: The *MEA 240 μg* maintained stable performance throughout the measurement period. In contrast, low-loading MEAs, such as the depicted *MEA 30 μg* , exhibit a decline in performance over the same timeframe. In addition, as discussed in the main text, the IV curve of the *MEA 30 μg* in cycle 3 shows signs of mass transport limitation at voltages approaching 2.0 V. This feature diminishes over the course of the measurement.

Figure S7: Specific current density as a function of Pt loading. The specific current density j_{spec} was calculated by normalizing the current density j to the total noble metal loading, defined as the sum of iridium and platinum loading.

Figure S8: IV curves of cycle 6 of samples *MEA 7.5 μg* and *MEA 7.5 $\mu\text{g v2}$* and *MEA 7.5 $\mu\text{g v3}$* . The graph again demonstrates the high reproducibility of the sputter-etching treatment and magnetron sputtering process, confirming the consistency of the MEAs in the low-Pt-loading range of tested samples.

Figure S9: Time evolution of current densities normalized to their maximal value. Cycle 1 represents the cycle with the highest performance for each MEA. All data were measured at 2.0 V. While a significant performance decline is observed for most MEAs at 1.5 V (Fig. 3), the performance drop is considerably less pronounced at higher voltages. *MEA 30 μg* was omitted from this graph due to its mass transport limitation behavior at higher voltages (see Fig. S6).

Figure S10: Time evolution of current density of *MEA 60 μg* normalized to the maximum current density at specific voltages, corrected for the ohmic drop ($U_{corr} = U - jR_{\Omega}$). Despite the value of 1.7 V of corrected voltage corresponds to almost 2.0 V of cell voltage, the degradation evolution is very similar to lower voltages. This confirms that different degradation magnitude for different voltages in Fig. 3 and Fig. S9 is due to the effect of ohmic resistance.

Figure S11: IV curves for all samples and their measurement cycles. All graphs have identical horizontal and vertical axis.

Figure S12: Time evolution of ohmic resistance for the *MEA 480 μg* and its non-etched counterpart, *MEA 480 μg plain*, at 1.45 V. The non-etched *MEA 480 μg plain* exhibits a rapid drop between the first and second cycle (the first data point is not shown), suggesting low porosity for hydrogen mass transport. However, after this initial change, the non-etched sample shows lower ohmic resistance, possibly due to better catalyst connectivity to the GDL.

Figure S13: Time evolution of ohmic resistance for the *MEA 120 μg* and its non-etched counterpart, *MEA 120 μg plain*, at 1.45 V, showing similar trends as for the pair of *MEA 480 μg* and *MEA 480 μg plain*, depicted in Fig. S12.

Figure S14: Time evolution of cathodic capacitance of *MEA 480 μg* and its non-etched counterpart, *MEA 480 μg plain*, at 1.45 V. The etched *MEA 480 μg* exhibits several times higher capacitance, indicating that the sputter-etching treatment increases the active surface area of the catalyst.

Figure S15: Ohmic resistance after assembly (cycle 1) at cell voltage of 1.39 V. Samples with Pt loading exceeding 20 μg_{Pt} cm⁻² showed comparable resistance values of approximately 100 mΩ cm². However, for samples with lower Pt loading, the resistance increased significantly, indicating reduced lateral connectivity of platinum particles on the sputter-etched membrane at ultra-low loadings.

Figure S16: The highest performance IV curves of *MEA 240 μg* and *MEA GDE* without and with ohmic drop correction ($U_{corr} = U - jR_{\Omega}$). The lower ohmic resistance of *MEA 240 μg* explains its superior performance compared to *MEA GDE*. After correcting for ohmic resistance, their performances become similar, with *MEA GDE* even outperforming *MEA 240 μg* at lower voltages.

Figure S17: Performance of *MEA 15 μg* over three cycles, shown without and with correction for ohmic resistance. The increase in ohmic resistance alone does not fully explain the observed performance degradation.

Charge transfer resistance and Tafel slope

Our system model consists of ohmic resistance and two electrodes (Fig. S5). It is common to describe the kinetics of each electrode using a logarithmic relationship between the overpotential η and current density j [1-3]:

$$\eta = b \log\left(\frac{j}{j_0}\right), \quad (\text{S1})$$

where parameter b is the Tafel slope, and j_0 is the exchange current density for the given electrode. Incorporating Ohm's law, the total cell voltage E can be expressed as [4, 5]:

$$E = E_0 + E_\Omega + \eta_c + \eta_a = E_0 + R_\Omega j + b_c \log\left(\frac{j}{j_{0,c}}\right) + b_a \log\left(\frac{j}{j_{0,a}}\right)$$

where $E_0 = 1.18 \text{ V}$ is the reversible electrolysis voltage at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the subscripts c, a denote the cathode and anode, respectively, and E_Ω accounts for the voltage drop due to the ohmic resistance R_Ω . The charge transfer resistance R for both electrode reactions is defined as [6, 7]:

$$R_c = \frac{d\eta_c}{dj} = \frac{b_c}{j \ln 10}, \quad R_a = \frac{d\eta_a}{dj} = \frac{b_a}{j \ln 10}.$$

Thus, plotting $1/R$ against j should give a linear dependence with a slope of $\ln 10 / b$. By fitting these data, we can independently determine the Tafel slope for both the cathode and the anode (Fig. S10).

Additionally, the sum of b_c and b_a can be extracted from the IV characteristics. After correcting for the ohmic resistance, the kinetic voltage can be expressed as:

$$E_{\text{corr}} = E - R_\Omega j = (b_a + b_c) \log j + (E_0 - b_c \log j_{0,c} - b_a \log j_{0,a})$$

where the sum $b_a + b_c$ corresponds to the slope in a linear fit of voltage against the logarithm of current density (Fig. S14).

From the derived equations, it is evident that neither the corrected IV curves fitting nor the charge transfer resistance analysis allows us to determine the exchange current densities for the cathode and anode separately. However, the impedance spectroscopy analysis provides valuable insight into the processes inside the system by yielding the Tafel slopes.

Figure S18: Example of cathodic and anodic Tafel slope determination from charge transfer resistances for *MEA 60 μg* in cycle 5.

Figure S19: Example of total Tafel slope determination from the IV curve for *MEA 30 μg* in cycle 7.

Figure S20: Time evolution of the anodic Tafel slopes. These values exhibited greater stability compared to the cathodic slopes. In cycle 4, water starvation of *MEA* $120 \mu\text{g}$ led to an unreliable data point that cannot be appropriately interpreted.

Figure S21: Time evolution of the Tafel slopes for the *MEA* $30 \mu\text{g}$. The cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes, determined from charge transfer resistance analysis, are shown. Their sum is comparable to the Tafel slope obtained from the ohmic resistance corrected IV curves, confirming the consistency of the analysis.

Figure S22: Example of two distinct regimes with different Tafel slopes, with the transition current j_{trans} for $MEA\ 3.7\ \mu\text{g}$ in cycle 11.

References

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